

ELIMINATION OF LEAKAGE IN 3D PRINTED HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTICS FOR HYDROGEN-BASED DISTRIBUTION SYSTEMS

Florian Fuchs^{1,2}, Denni H. Rauschenberg^{1,2}, Fabian Mußbach^{1,2}, Marc Mayer², Eugen Musienko¹, Marc Fette^{1,2}, Jens P. Wulfsberg¹

¹ Laboratory for Manufacturing Technology at Helmut-Schmidt-University,
Holstenhofweg 85
Hamburg (Germany) 22043

² Composite Technology Center / CTC GmbH (An AIRBUS Company)
Airbus-Strasse 1
Stade (Germany) 21684

Email: florian.fuchs@hsu-hh.de , florian.f.fuchs@airbus.com

ABSTRACT

In face of its high flammability and explosiveness the safe containment of hydrogen is a critical challenge due to its high volatility and permeability. In aviation, where hydrogen is increasingly explored as a clean fuel alternative, ensuring leak-proof storage and distribution is essential. Additive manufacturing offers a promising approach for producing complex, lightweight components using high-performance thermoplastics. However, the inherent porosity and defects introduced during the fused deposition modeling (FDM) printing process pose a significant challenge for achieving airtight structures. This study investigates process adaptations to reduce porosity and eliminate macroscopic leakage to enhance the airtightness of FDM printed components as a preliminary step towards permeability measurements. A series of hollow test specimens were produced under varying process parameters with the aim of producing fully sealed layers. The specimens were tested for their airtightness through practical underwater leak tests. Additionally, their porosity was analyzed through X-ray computed tomography scans. These tests provide an efficient solution for identifying manufacturing parameters that minimize defects before proceeding to more complex full-scale permeability assessments. The findings contribute for enabling the use of additive manufacturing processes for hydrogen containment applications, ensuring safer and more reliable storage and distribution solutions in aerospace and other hydrogen-driven industries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen, the smallest and lightest element, has long been studied for its potential as an energy source. Even though the invention of the fuel cell took place over 150 years ago most modern methods of transport, including airplanes, rely on the use of easier to handle fossil fuels [1]. It is due to growing urgency to decarbonize travel that hydrogen has gained renewed interest as an alternative to conventional jet fuels. Unlike stationary storage, or land and sea-based transportation systems, where hydrogen may be stored in highly pressurized tanks or in chemical carriers such as metal hydrides, aerospace applications require lightweight containment solutions which meet strict mass and space limitations [1, 2].

Advanced manufacturing methods such as additive manufacturing of high-performance thermoplastics offer a promising path for producing lightweight, geometrically complex components, that meet these limitations [3]. Especially fused deposition modelling (FDM) enables the production of large scale, custom parts with reduced lead times. However, the

layer wise deposition of individual polymer filaments inherent to FDM printing may lead to structural defects such as porosity, interconnecting voids and poor layer bonding, all of which compromise the integrity and airtightness of components [4]. In the face of hydrogens ability to easily penetrate through materials and exploit microscopic defects, the elimination of such leakage pathways is critical [5].

This study focuses on the optimization of process parameters to minimize porosity and eliminate macroscopic leakage in FDM processed high-performance thermoplastics. To this end a series of hollow test specimens were fabricated under varying parameters to assess their influence in producing fully sealed layers. Leak tightness was evaluated through submerged pressure tests in a water bath, while internal porosity was characterized using X-ray computed tomography (XCT) scans. These preliminary assessments provide practical means of identifying suitable process conditions that allow the manufacturing of airtight components before advancing to more advanced permeability measurements. The findings aim to assist the use of additively manufactured components in hydrogen storage and distribution solutions in aerospace and other weight sensitive applications.

2. METHODS & EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Sample manufacturing

Several hollow specimen sets were produced from high performance thermoplastics utilizing the high temperature FDM print system “Funmat Pro 610 HT” of Intamsys. This study focuses on the assessment of polymers belonging to the group of Polyaryletherketones (PAEK), Thermoplastic Polyimides (TPI) and Polyphenylene Sulfides (PPS). As shown in Figure 1 each specimen set is made up of a cylinder with parallelly stacked layers and two pyramids with increasing layer shifts through overhang angles of 20° and 40° respectively. As such the specimens were selected to represent a broad range of print conditions with increasing criticality. Each specimen is designed to avoid the need for support structure and is realized with a constant wall thickness. Sets were produced with wall thicknesses of 2.4, 4.0 and 5.6 mm as defined as multiples of the 0.8 mm nozzle diameter.

Figure 1: Hollow leakage specimen set made up of a cylinder (left) and two pyramids with 20° overhang (center) and 40° overhang (right)

As can be seen in Figure 2 FDM components usually suffer from structural defects caused by the extrusion process which impair their ability to contain gases or liquids [4, 6]. To eliminate such defects and improve the structural integrity of components, the print strategy must be adapted in a way to ensure effective bonding between extrudates and layers [7].

Figure 2: SEM images of characteristic defects between extrudates in FDM components [6]

This may be achieved through overlapping extrudates onto each other as depicted in Figure 3 or through increasing the flow rate to compensate for residual gaps [7]. Following the depicted print strategy, it proved to be effective to incorporate a visual approach for determining suitable parameter levels for flow rate and overlap percentage, resulting in fully sealed layers.

Figure 3: Extrusion strategies to maximize precision (left) or eliminate voids (right) [7]

As such, throughout this study leakage was evaluated over changes in the material flow rate and infill overlap percentage while other parameters were kept constant to material specific indications based on available processing information by the material supplier. These basic manufacturing parameters are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Basic print parameters

Polymer	Nozzle [°C]	Chamber [°C]	Print speed [mm/s]	Layer height [mm]	Nozzle size [mm]
TPI (ThermaX)	390	230	120	0.2	0.8
PAEK (AM 200)	390	160	35	0.2	0.8
PPS (AM 230)	315	70	50	0.2	0.8

2.2 Leak tests

Leakage was evaluated according to the submerged bubble tests as defined in DIN EN 1779. The bubble test is not suited for determining a leakage rate but provides a simple and efficient solution in qualitatively evaluating the airtightness of components and localizing areas of leakage [8]. Figure 4 shows the basic test setup as well as a prepared specimen consisting out of a pressure regulator, water bath, sample fixtures, camera and a connector which is tightly

screwed into the specimen. During testing the prepared specimen is connected to the pressure supply and submerged into the water bath. Afterwards the pressure is increased through the regulator in steps of 0.5 bar up to a maximum of roughly 7.5 bar until a leak can be detected. The camera captures potential leaks in the form of bubble streams emerging from the specimen.

Figure 4: Leakage test setup: pressure regulator (left); water bath and fixtures (center); prepared specimen (right).

2.3 X-ray computed tomography for the analysis of internal defects

X-ray computed tomography has proven to be a reliable method in the field of non-destructive material testing for assessing the structural integrity of tested components, particularly regarding their resistance to the formation of structural defects such as interconnected pores, which may directly lead to leakage [9, 10].

The samples were examined at a voltage of 200 kV and a current of 237 μ A, which was determined by the Zeiss METROTOM 1500 system depending on the detector and positioning system. For the detector settings, an integration time of 2000 ms was set at a magnification of 2.0x without an image center. All samples were set in the positioning system at a target distance from X-ray source to sample of $x = 250$ mm. The result of these settings was a focal spot size of 47 μ m with a voxel size of 38.66 μ m. These are not optimal values as the size of the focal spot compared to the voxel size leads to a certain blurring. To minimize over- or underestimation of pore counts, clusters containing fewer than 30 contiguous voxels were excluded from the analysis, thereby eliminating artifacts induced by the XCT. Consequently, genuine pores below this threshold may not have been detected.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Sample manufacturing and leakage

Figure 5 shows the evolution of parameter levels representatively for PPS specimens. As can be seen, voids are continuously eliminated through increases in flow rate and overlap percentage. Simultaneously, surface finish and geometrical accuracy are impaired. The final parameter levels for PPS were an increased flow rate of 105 % and an overlap of 40 %.

Figure 5: Visual development of parameters through elimination of voids: Flow rate 100 %, Overlap 30 % (left); Flow rate 102 %, Overlap 40 % (center); Flow rate 105 %, Overlap 40 % (right)

The developed parameters were validated through leak testing as described in section two. Figure 6 shows a corresponding test specimen set with wall thicknesses of 5.6 mm.

Figure 6: PPS leakage specimen set

All optimized specimens proved to be fully airtight up to pressures of around 7.5 bar which represents the maximum test pressure. No correlation between wall thickness and airtightness could be observed. As such parameter levels that resulted in airtightness in thicker specimens transferred this behavior to specimens with thinner wall thicknesses down to 2.4 mm. Comparable results were accomplished for PAEK and TPI specimen. The development resulted in a flow rate of 100 % and overlap percentage of 25 % for both PAEK and TPI respectively.

Figure 7 shows images captured during testing of TPI cylinders manufactured with varying flow rates ranging from 97 % to 100 %. The images capture the development of airtightness alongside changes in flow rate. As can be seen there is a significant reduction in bubble streams exiting the specimen from left to right until complete sealing is achieved.

Figure 7: Comparison of leakage in TPI cylinders with 5.6 mm wall thickness at a testing pressure of 0.5 bar. Flow rates from left to right: 97 %, 98 %, 100 %

To correlate the development of airtightness with changes in the internal structure a detailed XCT analysis has been performed for the shown specimens.

3.2 Results of the X-ray computed tomography

The following section presents the key findings from the XCT analysis. Using Dragonfly 3D software, the pore volume fraction was determined for each sample. Table 2 summarizes the pore characteristics of the samples with 5.6 mm wall thickness and different flow rate factors.

Table 2: Key parameters of the analyzed specimens

Sample No.	Flow Rate [%]	Leakage	Pore Volume Fraction [%]	Max Pore Volume [mm ³]	Max feret diameter [mm]
1	97	high	2.92	7.99	22.96
2	98	moderate	1.83	8.68	13.96
3	100	none	1.29	4.68	10.56

As shown in Table 2, increasing the flow rate from 97 % to 100 % is associated with a gradual decrease in pore volume fraction, maximum pore volume, and maximum feret diameter. This trend coincides with a reduction in leakage, ranging from high at 97 % flow rate to none at 100 % flow rate. These observations suggest that higher flow rates may contribute to a denser internal structure with fewer and smaller pores resulting in gradually reduced leakage.

Although the data shown in the table do not permit definitive conclusions regarding pore interconnectivity, the observed correlation between reduced porosity and reduced leakage supports the hypothesis that larger and potentially interconnected pores may serve as preferential pathways for gas flow. This interpretation is further substantiated by a cross-sectional XCT image of the three samples in which a large, interconnected pore, as highlighted in Figure 8, is distinctly visible in Sample 1, which was produced with the lowest flow rate. The presence of such a continuous pore structure strengthens the assumption that

interconnected porosity can significantly contribute to leakage, particularly in specimens fabricated with suboptimal extrusion parameters. In contrast, the other two samples in the cross-sectional image also show pores, but these are not visibly interconnected, which may explain their lower leakage levels despite the presence of residual porosity.

Figure 8: XCT cross-section of samples produced with varying flow rates. Flow rates from left to right: 97 %, 98 %, 100 %

Figure 9 shows a similar trend across the longitudinal axis. The left sample manufactured with a flow rate of 97 % exhibits larger and partially interconnected pores across the specimen thickness. In contrast, pores in samples produced with higher flow rates (98 % and 100 %) seem to be isolated without visible interconnections. This visual comparison suggests that an increased flow rate effectively reduces the occurrence of critical pore structures and thereby improves the airtightness of printed parts.

Figure 9: Longitudinal XCT cross-section of samples produced with varying flow rates. Flow rates from left to right: 97 %, 98 %, 100 %

Overall, the data supports the hypothesis that lower flow rates result in increased interconnected porosity and poorer structural coherence, which significantly elevate the likelihood of leakage. These observations highlight the importance of optimized extrusion parameters in ensuring structural integrity during material deposition processes.

4. CONCLUSION

This study incorporated a multilayered test and analysis approach for the elimination of macroscopic leakage in several high-performance thermoplastics that are processed via FDM printing. The underlying print strategy adaptations involved deliberate over-extrusion via increases in flow rate and overlap percentage, promoting bonding of individual extrudates and structural integrity. These adaptations were carried by a combination of visual optimizations as well as submerged bubble tests inside a water bath, both of which combined proved to be highly efficient in reducing number and severeness of leak sites across different geometrical shapes. A further detailed evaluation of the internal structure of tested components alongside changes in the aforementioned parameters suggests a correlation between pore size, volume fraction, and interconnectivity with the occurrence of leaks. The evolution of the internal structure at a reference layer was captured through different flow rates and compared. As a result, a higher flow rate generally seems to contribute to gradually filling voids promoting airtightness. As such the material specific optimizations resulted in fully airtight specimen up to an internal pressure of 7.5 bar across all studied thermoplastics and shapes. Surprisingly the wall thickness of specimen seemed to have no effect on this property. The findings contribute to the utilization of FDM printed components in pressurized gas or liquid containment systems in aviation or other mobility sectors. Furthermore, the effective elimination of macroscopic leakage allows for a further assessment of microscopic permeability, necessary for hydrogen storage and distribution applications. Finally, this study expands the usability of FDM printing technology for the direct manufacturing of functional components and highlights the importance of the print strategy in achieving desirable part performance.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] T. T. Le *et al.*, "Fueling the future: A comprehensive review of hydrogen energy systems and their challenges," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 54, pp. 791–816, 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.08.044. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360319923039988>
- [2] McKinsey & Company, Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking, and Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking, *Hydrogen-powered aviation: A fact-based study of hydrogen technology, economics, and climate impact by 2050*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2020.
- [3] A. H. Alami *et al.*, "Additive manufacturing in the aerospace and automotive industries: Recent trends and role in achieving sustainable development goals," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 14, no. 11, 2023, Art. no. 102516, doi: 10.1016/j.asej.2023.102516.
- [4] E. G. Gordeev, A. S. Galushko, and V. P. Ananikov, "Improvement of quality of 3D printed objects by elimination of microscopic structural defects in fused deposition modeling," *PloS one*, early access. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0198370.
- [5] X. Li, Q. Huang, Y. Liu, B. Zhao, and J. Li, "Review of the Hydrogen Permeation Test of the Polymer Liner Material of Type IV On-Board Hydrogen Storage Cylinders," *Materials (Basel, Switzerland)*, early access. doi: 10.3390/ma16155366.
- [6] N. Naveed, "Investigating the Material Properties and Microstructural Changes of Fused Filament Fabricated PLA and Tough-PLA Parts," *Polymers*, early access. doi: 10.3390/polym13091487.
- [7] I. Gibson, D. Rosen, B. Stucker, and M. Khorasani, *Additive Manufacturing Technologies*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- [8] *DIN EN 1779:1999-10, Non-destructive testing - Leak testing - Criteria for method and technique selection; English version of DIN EN 1779:1999*, Berlin.
- [9] S. Evsevlev *et al.*, "X-ray Computed Tomography Procedures to Quantitatively Characterize the Morphological Features of Triply Periodic Minimal Surface Structures," *Materials (Basel, Switzerland)*, early access. doi: 10.3390/ma14113002.
- [10] D. Bernard, F. Léonard, E. Plougouven, and G. Bruno, "On the use of autocorrelation functions, permeability tensors, and computed tomography to characterise the anisotropy of diesel particulate filter materials," *Philosophical Magazine*, vol. 100, no. 22, pp. 2802–2835, 2020, doi: 10.1080/14786435.2020.1798532.